

The Unjournal

Evaluation 1 of "The Macroeconomic Impact of Climate Change: Global vs. Local Temperature"

Evaluator 1

Published on: Jan 11, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.cd61ce83/0289a274>

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